

TEACHING CRITICAL THINKING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract. Learning English is a priority task of modern education. A huge amount of information comes to us precisely from English-language resources, in order to freely navigate it and select the right one, the student must think critically.

Keywords: Critical thinking, English, schoolchildren, education, method, language, step.

INTRODUCTION

The study of foreign languages has become an integral part of the life of a modern person. The most necessary foreign language for education is English. The study of English and other foreign languages begins in primary school. The main goal of modern school education is to educate a person who is able to think perfectly and who has the skills to live in a competitive and high-tech world. Therefore, in order to live and develop in the modern world, it is necessary to learn foreign languages.

Critical thinking is the ability to ask questions, develop a variety of arguments, and make independent, thoughtful decisions. Therefore, the main idea of using technology for me is to create such an atmosphere of learning through play techniques, in which students, together with the teacher, actively communicate, consciously reflect on the learning process, track, confirm, refute or expand knowledge, new ideas, feelings or opinions about the world around them. .

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of critical thinking in English lessons is an innovative approach to the educational process, in which the goal of education is to develop students' opportunities to master new experiences. The basis of such development is the purposeful formation of creative and critical thinking, experience and tools of educational and research activities, role-playing and simulation modeling, search and definition of one's own personal meanings and value relations.

The main feature of the technology for the development of critical thinking, "is the "construction" of one's own knowledge within the framework of one's own search activity."

The development of rational, critical thinking has been one of the educational goals generally recognized in foreign pedagogy for decades. In socio-pedagogical terms, its importance is associated with the idea of a democratic society relying on balanced critical thinking of citizens and the ability to make well-considered, balanced decisions associated with it.

The core of the development of intellectual skills is critical thinking.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This technology allows strong students to develop their talents, students with average abilities to achieve new positive results, and students with insufficient motivation to learn to experience success.

It is important to note that when using the technology for the development of critical thinking, the acquisition of new knowledge does not begin with familiarity with known methods for solving a particular task or problem, but with the creation of conditions that form the need to obtain a solution to this particular problem. By answering personally significant questions that arise on the way to the goal, a person can master new material faster and deeper.

The main stages of the lesson when using the "Critical Thinking" technology are the stage of challenge, comprehension, reflection.

The first stage is the challenge.

This stage allows you to update and summarize the student's knowledge on a given topic or problem; arouse a steady interest in the topic under study, motivate the student to learning activities.

At the challenge stage, using various techniques (individual/pair/group work, brainstorming; content prediction; problem questions, etc.) and communicate in their own words what they know to the whole class.

Thus, previously acquired knowledge is brought to the level of awareness. Now they can become the basis for the assimilation of new knowledge, which gives students the opportunity to more effectively connect new information with previously known.

The second stage is comprehension. This stage allows the student to receive new information, comprehend it, correlate it with existing knowledge, analyze new information and existing knowledge.

Be critical in understanding new information.

At the stage of comprehension, when the student comes into contact with new information or ideas by reading a text, watching a movie, listening to lectures, he learns to track his understanding and not ignore gaps, but write down in the form of questions what he did not understand for clarification in the future.

The third stage is reflection.

The main thing here is: a holistic understanding, generalization of the information received, the formation of each student's own attitude to the material being studied.

At the stage of reflection, students reflect on the connection with what they learned in the lesson, reinforcing new knowledge, actively rebuilding their ideas in order to include new concepts in them. A lively exchange of ideas between students

gives them the opportunity to get acquainted with different points of view, teaches them to listen carefully to a friend, and defend their opinion with arguments.

CONCLUSION

Technology gives the student:

- increasing the efficiency of information perception;
- increasing interest both in the material being studied and in the learning process itself;
- the ability to think critically;
- the ability to take responsibility for one's own education;
- the desire and ability to become a person who learns throughout life.

Technology gives the teacher:

- the ability to create an atmosphere of openness and responsible cooperation in the classroom;
- the ability to use a learning model and a system of effective methods that contribute to the development of critical thinking and independence in the learning process;
- become practitioners who can competently analyze their activities;
- become a source of valuable professional information for other teachers.

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